

Original Research Article

What Makes ‘Sensational’ Sexual Crime Stories on the Front Pages? A Critical Analysis of News Values

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ABSTRACT

To answer the deceptively simple question of ‘what makes the popular sexual crime stories?’ this study content analyses all the front page news articles (N = 502) on sexual violence that were published in the *The Times of India* (New Delhi edition), *Hindustan Times* (New Delhi edition) and *The Telegraph* (Kolkata edition), popular Indian English newspapers, during an examination window (1 January 2023 to 31 December 2024), which covered 731 days. It measures the prevalence of and the priority accorded to popular news values, identifying their patterns. Dramatic and conflict-oriented news accounts that were personalised (with a human-interest angle) and presented as an extraordinary case of sexual assault emerged as the predominant pattern of page-one stories on sexual crime on these broadsheets. This was also the news pattern that was most closely associated with sensationalism. Nevertheless, politicised sexual crime stories that involved the power elite and celebrities or the developing stories that centred around superlatives were prioritised.

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Introduction

In contemporary times, crimes against women—especially sexual violence—are topical and there has been a consistent escalation in the registration of violent crimes against women in India, including gang rape, as illustrated in the official statistics (NCRB, 2023). NCRB (2023) statistics showed a consistent increase in the registration of crimes against women, with the number of cases rising from 3,71,503 in 2020 to 4,28,278 in 2021 and then to 4,45,256 in 2022.

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As many as 29,670 cases of rape were recorded among 4,48,211 cases of crimes against women in 2023, as per the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB).

Just a fraction of those cases of sexual violence in India are reported in the newspapers and this study aims to understand what determines news selection and prioritisation, identifying the ingredients that make the popular sexual crime stories that are highlighted on the front pages. Accordingly, the primary objectives of the present study are to analyse the nuanced aspects of sexual crimes highlighted in popular news stories and to examine how these factors influence news presentation and prioritisation.

While Walter Lippmann (1922) is credited with first suggesting “attributes or conventions” for news selection (Caple & Bednarek, 2013), Galtung and Ruge (1965) laid the formal foundations for news values, deeming them as factors determining news selection and prioritisation to answer the “deceptively simple” question of “what is news?”, Galtung and Ruge (1965) introduced “frequency, threshold, unambiguity, meaningfulness, consonance, unexpectedness, continuity, composition, reference to elite nations, reference to elite people, reference to persons and reference to something negative” as news values determining news selection. A series of studies followed in the following decades, reexamining and altering this list of news values (Harcup & O’Neill, 2001; Allern, 2002; McGregor, 2002; O’Neill & Harcup, 2009; Caple & Bednarek, 2016; Harcup & O’Neill, 2017). For instance, Harcup and O’Neill revisited Galtung and Ruge’s influential taxonomy of news values (Galtung & Ruge, 1965) twice in this millennium to check their relevance in these changing times, with the latest effort considering the digital influence and the emergence of social media (Harcup & O’Neill, 2001; Harcup & O’Neill, 2017). While Harcup & O’Neill (2001) altered the list of news values (the power elite, celebrity, entertainment, surprise, bad news, good news, magnitude, relevance, follow-up, newspaper agenda) at the turn of this millennium, they revisited the list (Harcup & O’Neill, 2017) to further revise it to: “Exclusivity, bad news, conflict, surprise, audio-visuals, shareability, entertainment, drama, follow-up, the power elite, relevance, magnitude, celebrity, good news and news organisation’s agenda”. Many recent works have also discussed news values in contemporary times (Fuller, 1996; Bednarek & Caple, 2014; Bednarek, 2016; Barclay, 2024).

News values have also been variously defined as the determinants of “what is news” (Brighton & Foy, 2007; Cotter, 2010); criteria that determine the likelihood of an event becoming news (Westerståhl & Johansson, 1994; Palmer, 2000) employing a deterministic approach and

focussing on story selection; measures of newsworthiness (Galtung & Ruge, 1965; Hartley, 1982; Bell, 1991; Fowler, 1991; Tunstall, 1996); and “the (imagined) preferences of the expected audience” (Richardson, 2007, p. 94), all centered around newsworthiness, either based on the event, the judgement of the journalists or socially-constructed assumptions. While the traditional understanding of news values is grounded either in a material perspective—that is, for instance, news selection is based on what has occurred (event) or who is involved (popular people?)—or in a cognitive perspective—based on the assumptions of the news reporters and editors about newsworthiness and rooted in cognitive psychology. Caple and Bednarek (2016) offered a discursive perspective to news values, complementing those perspectives. According to them, “News values are also constructed in the discourses involved in the production of news” (p. 435) and conceptualised newsworthiness as the “worth of a happening or issue to be reported as news, as established via a set of news values (such as Negativity, Proximity)” (p. 436).

Accordingly, the primary objectives of the study are stated as:

- To measure the paper-wise prevalence of and priority accorded to news values
- To identify the patterns of news values in the popular sexual crime stories and associate them with news sensationalism and priority

Research method

In this study, which aims to understand what makes sensational sexual crime news stories in India, a quantitative content analysis research design is employed, selecting a sample of popular news discourse and manually analysing it using a coding instrument. As a sample of the popular news discourse, the front pages of *The Times of India* (New Delhi edition), *Hindustan Times* (New Delhi edition) and *The Telegraph* (Kolkata edition), India’s popular English-language newspapers, were selected based on the availability of e-paper archives. Reviewing the front pages of these newspapers for 731 days (1 January 2023 to 31 December 2024), all news articles on sexual crimes were collected for further analysis using a census sampling technique. A total of 502 news articles were identified and analysed during this period. The unit of analysis was a news article, published on the front pages of the newspaper, including brief news. From those newspaper front pages, news articles that were on sexual violence against women were chosen for analysis.

Adapting from Barclay and Laskar (2025), a coding book and structured instrument were developed for the content analysis of the news articles sampled from the front pages.

The factors measured in the instrument include Publication (TOI, HT, and TT), Sensationalism, News Values and News Priority. To outline the coding instrument, the factors, their descriptions, categories, and measurements are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables and measurement

Factor	Description or categories	Measurement
Publication	TOI, HT, TT	Nominal
Priority	Article hierarchy on page (Reversed) * Number of columns	Scale
News values	Progression, Threshold, The power elite, Celebrity, Personalisation, Conflict, Unexpectedness, Drama, Political, Caste, Visual impact, Hyperdetail and Exclusive	Absent, Unsure, Mildly present (implicit or subdued), Strongly present (explicit or foregrounded)
Sensationalism	Prioritising exciting, exaggerated or shocking content over factual accuracy and objective reporting for emotional appeal and capturing public attention	Absent, Unsure, Mildly present (moderate or implicit), Strongly present (explicit or extreme)

Items for measuring news values were adapted from Barclay (2024) and Barclay and Laskar (2025). The news values chosen for the study were Progression (the news is developing: current news event that has just happened with imminent implications, unfolding or ongoing), Threshold (exhibiting superlativeness [large scope or scale of an event or issue] and impact [high significance of an event or issue in terms of its effects or consequences]), the Power elite (news involves influential individuals, institutions, organisations and corporations), Celebrity (involves an already famous person), Personalisation (news presents a human-interest angle), Conflict (presents conflicts or disagreements), Unexpectedness (presents news as extraordinary, odd, shocking, extreme or gruesome), Drama (presents an element of drama), Political (presents a political angle), Caste (presents a caste angle), Visual impact (features

dramatic, emotive, explicit, gory or impactful imagery or exquisite layout), Hyperdetail (presents micro details) and Exclusive (branded as a special or exclusive story).

Intercoder agreement between two expert coders (using five news items and 399 valid cases) was measured and found to be reliable, with a Cronbach's Alpha value above .80.

Findings

Using the coding instrument, the 502 sampled news articles on sexual crime published on the front pages of the three newspapers were analysed, and the chosen variables were measured. To illustrate the analysed data, the news outlet-wise frequencies of news articles on sexual crimes published on the front pages of those newspapers, their percentages, average article count per day, and the average priority accorded to an article are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. News outlet-wise article frequencies

Factors	TOI	HT	TT	Overall
Article count	252	167	83	502
Percentage	50.2	33.3	16.5	100
Average article count/day	0.35	0.23	0.11	0.69
Average priority/article	27.69	29.49	51.62	32.24

Of the total 502 articles on sexual violence published on the front pages of the sampled newspapers during the study period, TOI (*The Times of India*) published 252 articles, the HT (*Hindustan Times*) published 167 articles and TT (*The Telegraph*) published 83 articles. The average article count per day was 0.35 for the TOI, which meant that on average, a news item appeared once every three days on its front page. The HT had a frequency of 0.23, meaning that a news item appeared once every five days on average. Similarly, it was 0.11 for TT (once in 10 days on average).

The overall average article count a day for these newspapers was 0.69, which meant that once in two days, a sexual crime story appeared on one of those front pages.

While the TOI published the largest number of news articles on sexual crime (252) during the study period, the TT accorded the highest priority to sexual violence stories.

On the front pages, the average priority accorded to sexual violence stories across the newspapers during the study period was 32.24. To measure the paper-wise prevalence of and priority accorded to news values, sensationalism, crime types reported, topics covered, and regions of the crime, statistical tests were performed to calculate the frequencies and average news priority scores. The test results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Paper-wise frequencies and Priority averages

Factors	TOI (252)		HT (167)		TT (83)		Overall (502)	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
News values								
Progression	123	34.13	95	36.40	68	55.50	286	39.97
Threshold	98	33.42	58	39.31	62	59.08	218	42.28
The power elite	79	33.98	56	32.94	31	48.90	166	36.42
Celebrity	19	34.10	8	15.25	15	45.73	42	34.66
Personalisation	64	33.56	46	32.04	27	48.85	137	36.06
Conflict	70	36.31	39	36.51	27	59.62	136	41.0
Unexpectedness	94	27.19	72	31.59	28	56.57	194	33.06
Drama	69	31.04	52	32.15	26	52.73	147	35.27
Political	54	40.88	40	40.40	38	55.34	132	44.90
Caste	14	22.35	13	30.61	0	-	27	26.33
Visual impact	8	58.87	7	21.42	2	67.50	17	44.47
Hyperdetail	47	25.02	18	32.88	3	40.33	68	27.77
Exclusive	20	26.75	0	-	1	16.0	21	26.23
Sensationalism	83	29.74	40	34.35	25	58.28	147	35.85

F - Frequency; P - Average news priority

Progression, Threshold and Unexpectedness were the most prevalent news values across the newspapers. While the HT used Progression and Unexpectedness the most, the TT employed Progression and Threshold. The TOI recorded a high on all three of these values.

When it came to the priority accorded, the TOI offered the highest prominence to sexual violence news articles with a political angle and those with visual impact.

Meanwhile, the HT prioritised articles with the Threshold and Political values, while the TT reserved its prime spaces for conflict-based articles with the Threshold value.

Table 4. Factor analysis results

Patterns							
News value	1	2	3	4	5	Eigenvalues	Communalities
Drama	.834					3.252	.722
Personalisation	.799						.667
Unexpectedness	.767						.657
Conflict	.475						.519
Power_elite		.825				1.965	.718
Political		.775					.745
Celebrity		.671					.525
Progression			.875			1.292	.815
Threshold			.783				.730
Exclusive				.826		1.115	.704
Hyperdetail				.778			.657
Caste					.805	1.055	.656
Visual_impact					.730		.565
Sensationalism	.500**		.289**	.268**	.089*		
News priority		.164**	.425**	-.094*			

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Of the 502 news articles analysed, as many as 60 showed strong (explicit and extreme) signs of sensationalism, while in 87 others, it was mildly present (implicit or moderate). To identify the patterns of news values and associate them with sensationalism and news priority accorded in the popular news discourse, a factor analysis was performed and the results are presented in Table 4. An examination of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin measure of sampling adequacy suggested that the sample was factorable ($KMO = .740$) and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 1533.375, p < .0005$). For this extraction, Principal Component Analysis was employed, along with Varimax rotation with Kaiser normalisation (rotation was reported to have converged in five iterations). Five components were identified and their Eigenvalues were 3.252, 1.965, 1.292, 1.115 and 1.055.

In the first pattern of sexual crime stories identified, the news values of Drama, Personalisation, Unexpectedness and Conflict were the most likely to co-occur along with Sensationalism. That is, dramatic, personalised news accounts that centred around oddity or superlatives and were conflict-oriented were the ones that were hypersensationalised. Or it can also be interpreted as the conflict-oriented stories were sensationalised, adding drama and a human-interest angle to the news accounts and presenting them as unexpected (using terms such as “most brutal” and “shocking”). Nevertheless, the second pattern of news articles garnered priority on the front pages: sexual crime stories that offered a political angle, involved celebrities or the power elites. While the third pattern was dominated by the news values of Progression (developing events) and Threshold (sensationalised news accounts that garnered front-page priority), the fourth was characterised by exclusive, hyper-detailed news accounts. In the fifth pattern, exclusive news articles engaged in hyperdetailing.

While sensationalism was the most prominent in the first pattern of news values (dramatised, human-interest stories that highlighted conflict and presented sexual assault events as extraordinary on the front pages), developing and hyperdetailed news accounts showed moderate signs of sensationalism. The utmost news priority was accorded to news developing news stories and those involving politicisation and personalities.

Discussion

To critically answer “what makes the popular sexual crime stories?”, this study manually content analysed a small corpus of sexual crime news stories published on the front pages of three popular Indian English dailies, covering 731 days and about 1,50,000 words of news text. Analysis was helpful in measuring the prevalence of news values and the priority accorded to each of them on these front pages, identifying their prevalence patterns.

When priorities (importance accorded to news stories, deduced based on their positioning on the front pages and the number of columns) were measured and associated with the discursive ingredients that comprised those sexual crime stories, the analyses provided meaningful insights. For instance, the popular news values that were most recurrent in the front-page stories analysed were Progression, Threshold, and Unexpectedness; however, priority was accorded to news stories with Threshold, Political and Visual impact. That is, these were often developing sexual crime stories that presented the event as extraordinary and sent across “shockwaves”, the ones that politicised the sexual assault or presented a political angle with visual impact.

During the study period, sexual crime stories occupied the top-page one slot 89 times and appeared as the second lead on 63 occasions.

Sensationalism was more closely associated with the news values Threshold, Personalisation, Unexpectedness, Drama and Conflict. Dramatic-personalised news accounts that were progressing and centred around oddities or superlatives were the ones that were hypersensationalised. While aligning with the popular definitions of sensationalism as an empathetic (Graber, 1994) and dramatised (Wang & Cohen, 2009) emotional appeal to “human instinct” (Slattery & Hakanen, 1994) aimed to grab reader attention (Grabe et al., 2001), this news values-based approach and these findings broaden its scope, adding news values-based dimensions such as personalisation and hyperdetailing.

Furthermore, the study findings pointed to an editorial orientation inclined towards a conflict discourse in sexual crime stories, often involving the power elites or celebrities and indicating the politicisation of sexual violence.

During the two-year study period, 502 news stories were identified as covering sexual crimes on these newspaper front pages. Of them, 267 were either single-column or brief news stories, whereas 182 occupied two or three columns and 48 four or five columns. While Sreedharan and Thorsen (2021) decried the low prevalence of rape and sexual violence stories on newspaper front pages, these results point to frequent appearances.

Conclusion

To answer the deceptively simple question of ‘what makes the popular sexual crime stories?’ this study content analysed 502 front page news articles on sexual violence and measured the prevalence of and priority accorded to news values and sensationalism. Further, this study associated news values with sensationalism and identified the patterns of news values in the popular sexual crime stories. Dramatic and conflict-oriented articles that featured a human-interest angle and presented the occurrence as a case of extreme violence constituted the predominant pattern of sexual crime news stories published on the front pages of the chosen three broadsheets: *The Times of India*, *Hindustan Times* and *The Telegraph*. This was also the news pattern that was most closely associated with sensationalism. Nevertheless, politicised sexual crime stories that involved the power elite and celebrities or the developing stories that were centred around superlatives were the most prioritised.

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